

Motivational Factors of Small and Medium Enterprises in Mankweng Township (Zone 1), Limpopo Province

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Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) continue to play a crucial role in socioeconomic development by creating jobs and fostering economic growth in South African townships. This paper aims to investigate the motivational factors of SMEs in Mankweng Township (Zone 1). The question that this paper aims to answer is what are the motivational factors of SMEs in Mankweng Township (Zone 1)? Motivational factors in the business world refer to the driving forces that influence companies' choices, actions, and behavioural patterns. In the context of entrepreneurship, motivation can stem from internal desires such as ambition, independence, and achievement, or external pressures such as unemployment and financial need. This paper shows that overdependence on profit might overshadow the social responsibility of serving the local community. This paper used a mixed methods approach. This paper determines that it is essential to achieve profit or additional income while upholding the social responsibility of supporting the local community with dignity and respect. In the end, this paper suggests that to improve the sustainability and development of SMEs in South African townships, it is crucial to support both internal and external motivators that affect entrepreneurial actions.

Keywords: Capacity building, motivational factors, profit, small and medium enterprises, South Africa

Under the auspices of business, motivational factors refer to the driving forces that influence the actions, choices and patterns of enterprises (Dauletova & Al-Busaidi, 2024; Mizgajska, 2025; Nkoana & Mashamaite, 2025). Motivational factors determine why enterprise owners or persons decide to engage in certain economic activities and pursue specific goals. In the entrepreneurship context, motivation can emerge from internal desires such as achievement, ambition, and independence, or external pressures such as financial need and unemployment (Caliendo, Kritikos, & Stier, 2023). Undeclared, strong motivational factors assist entrepreneurs committed and focused on attaining success, even in a challenging business climate. Thus, understanding motivational factors cannot be postponed as it serves as crucial for explaining the sustainability and behaviour of the entrepreneur. This means that without the robust motivational elements, enterprises will not be able to thrive for more than 5 years of activity.

Akerle (2023) reveals that motivational factors play an important role in improving productivity and employee performance within a business. This suggests that in order to develop goal-oriented behaviour that is consistent with the objectives of the organisation, employees must be motivated. It is not a say but true that effective motivation stimulates

creativity, strengthens organisational loyalty and increases job satisfaction, all of which result in improved performance. According to Nkoana (2025), motivation assists in creating a conducive working environment that encourages dedication and innovation among workers. As a result, motivation factors serve as the link between individual effort and organisational success. Many SMEs in South Africa emerge as a strategy to unemployment and no or limited job opportunities rather than as a result of entrepreneurial vision, passion or long-term planning (Nkoana & Mashamaite, 2025). This behaviour of survival-driven motivation often leads to lack of sustainability and weak business foundations. Therefore, this article aims to investigate the motivational factors of SMEs in Mankweng Township (Zone 1).

Problem Statement

Scholars such as Ngo Ndjama and Van Der Westhuizen (2024) believe that SMEs reduce the socio-economic challenges in the local areas such as townships in South Africa, by fostering economic growth and creating jobs. SMEs in South African townships, in view of Bvuma and Marnewick (2020), Malgas and Zondi (2020), and Netshishivhe (2021) despite their significance, face challenges related to sustainability and growth. These challenges emerge from motivational factors that influence owners and operators. The literature on the motivation of what drives SME owners and managers is not something that one can find easily (it is quite limited), especially in townships. These sufficient impact on their business performance, resilience and innovation capacity (Nkoana, 2025). As a result, many SMEs are more likely to close their operation over time due to insufficient long-term planning.

The recent study done by Aisyah and Umami (2022) made it clear that motivational factors such as profit and additional income in many SMEs are prioritised, leading to a situation where SME owners, employees or managers no longer give most customers adequate attention. This implies that staff members do not care about the customers as their attention is only on profit or making extra income. Furthermore, more dependence on profit or extra income as

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a main motivator without considering other motivators often hinders sustainability, creativity and innovation if not used adequately and as advantageous. As per Kongolo (2010) and Varum and Rocha (2013) SMEs in most numbers stemmed as a strategy to address unemployment and increase job opportunities rather than as a result of long-term planning. This means that those ventures into the business to address unemployment and the need to survive are often found with sufficient skills, experience, or strategic planning. This may put SME sector in a vulnerable position as they would find it difficult to cope with market rivalry, economic changes and limited resources in townships.

Evidently, Nwuke and Adeola (2023) did not hesitate to proclaim that the deficiency of family legacy, passion and vision is present in most SMEs operating in townships, despite being seen as intrinsic motivations being recognised as important drivers of success of the entrepreneurship. However, in the opinion of Erlandsson, Berhie, and Dawit (2025) limited commitment to growth and innovation in the business is caused by many entrepreneurs who start businesses without a genuine interest or long-term purpose. This implies that SMEs that struggle to remain competitive or adapt to changing market landscapes exist without a proper vision and sufficient passion. Similarly, starting a business without attaching it to a family legacy may mean that there is close to little or zero continuity or generational investment to keep such enterprises going and be sustained over time.

Review of Literature

Market Opportunities

Market opportunities serve as one of the primary reasons why South African people open SMEs. One can attest that in the study done by Musabayana and Mutambara (2022) niche market opportunities must be identified before one hopes of entering SMEs. This implies that market opportunities available promote SMEs' success in South African townships. In contrast, SMEs in Tshwane Townships that do not respond to the market demand may not be able to provide products or services that do not address the existing gap (Dhlomo, 2017). This makes identifying certain market opportunities a priority in the planning of the starting of SMEs. Thus, Fatoki (2018) informs us that success and expansion of SMEs can only be seen and experienced by the smartest people who start SMEs after recognising market opportunities. This reduces the uncertainty of establishing a business that does not address local needs based on the personal feeling.

Investors need to be convinced before they can bring investment into SMEs, proper market opportunities serve as a magnet for investors (Fatoki, 2018). SMEs in Gauteng are attracted to capitalise on market opportunities that yield profits (Mlotshwa & Msimango-Galawe, 2020). A source of assistance and financing that can simplify the process for aspiring entrepreneurs. As profit is the main purpose of a business, it is also the main focus of an investor. Molobela (2021) also alludes to the fact that SMEs operating in Mankweng Township are likely to make money or be successful if they capitalise on market opportunities. An SME must continue to tap into market opportunities if it wishes to be seen as a successful business by its community.

As Mmusi (2020) suggests, SMEs in South Africa have to meet the current demand for those products and services that are required by customers. This could also benefit customers as they would get

satisfaction through acquiring what they required from SMEs. Thus, the current market is very crucial in the development and expansion of SMEs. As Mputle (2020) says, the recognition of the market opportunities is that small enterprises in the City of Johannesburg have to be innovative in meeting the current market needs as the economy is changing. Therefore, small enterprises created as a result of meeting a market opportunity will empower the employers and employees with the opportunity of working in a dynamic market with an element of innovativeness and flexibility.

Profitability

For SMEs to progress and ensure the sustainability of their business, profits are needed- Rajagopaul, Magwentshu and Kalidas (2020). Whereby SMEs were unable to meet their costs during the Covid-19 pandemic because they were not making any profits, which might also indicate that the image of South African SMEs is not good. For many individuals, making profits is the main aim of starting an SME. Whereby, as highlighted by Wellalage and Reddy (2020) owners of SMEs believe that the profits made from the business can be used for reinvestment in the business. This can thus facilitate growth of the business by developing new products or services, or can be used for marketing, etc. External investors in South African townships are mainly concerned with making a profit from SMEs (Mahohoma, 2020). Therefore, profitable SMEs will bring external investors. Profitable SMEs are considered to be lower risk investments, as compared to non-profitable SMEs, they are more likely to get financed for future projects that can enhance the growth of the SME. According to Mputle (2020), SMEs in Johannesburg will only be able to compete with large corporations if they start making profits. This is because in SMEs, the business owners cannot afford to invest money in research and development of products or services due to high costs, which cannot be afforded in SMEs. As highlighted by Selelo (2023) for SMEs to attain a competitive advantage in the market, they need to make profits, which can in turn be used for upgrading the premises of the business, as well as paying higher salaries to skilled graduates.

Passion and Vision

Mura and Kajzar (2019) and Suriyankietkaew, Krittayaruangroj, and Iamsawan (2022) assert that SME owners may not necessarily be driven by financial gain to start SMEs because they have an affinity for cultural heritage and aspire to promote this heritage through their respective businesses. Therefore, these SMEs owners may be passionate about celebrating cultural heritage. Most SME owners, who have an affinity for cultural heritage, are very skilled artisans making traditional crafts and clothing (Yang, Shafi, Song, & Yang, 2018). In a township context, some people are inspired by their local heritage and have started their SMEs as cultural tourism operators whereby they offer tours to historical places, traditional ceremonies and a chance for tourists to meet and hear from residents about their local customs and culture. Traditional healers also operate in the SME sector and this is attributed to the fact that they are very skilled and tourists often visit these traditional healers because they sell local herbs and also assist tourists in going for spiritual healing, as they have experienced it in Africa in terms of culture and traditions (Petersen, Moll, Hockings, & Collins, 2015). Other entrepreneurs have started SMEs in the township areas where they cook and prepare meals such as "pap, chakalaka and braai" for tourists with the belief that tourists and residents will be interested in experiencing life in the township (Mahopo et al., 2022).

Family Legacy

Maharajh (2021) citing research has shown that in towns in KZN, family heritage is a determining factor in the establishment and survival of SMEs. Maharajh (2021) further holds that legacy instils a sense of duty and pride in continuing with the entrepreneurial zeal and the businesses founded by their ancestors. This points to the fact that SME owners in this era see their businesses as economically viable enterprises and also as legacy assets that are instrumental in preserving and safeguarding their ancestral heritage and customs, traditions and culture. This strong connection to ancestral heritage compels family members to carry on and extend their family businesses and in so doing, ensure that these businesses will continue to grow and evolve from generation to generation (Semenya, 2019). Semanya (2019) citing for instance the case of a customary king in Moletjie Moshate in Limpopo province, further states that many traditional leaders like King Moletjie Moshate own businesses, which they are extremely proud of and consider a great responsibility.

The family legacy within SMEs in the Eastern Cape is rich with the wealth of knowledge and skills in the businesses that have been built and passed on over generations of families (Sixaba, 2022). Passing on knowledge from one generation to another is useful to the young upcoming entrepreneurs, who can then make use of it in their own businesses by applying it to situations they may not be aware of. When children of small enterprise owners are asked where they assisted their parents in the SME, pupils would respond that during school holidays, they assisted their parents in the business as well as during weekends when they were not busy with schoolwork. By assisting their parents during holidays and on weekends, they felt confident and knowledgeable enough to solve any problems that would arise in the business (Mokoena, 2022). A family legacy can be seen as having a supportive nature between family members where they are able to share skills, assets and connections that support the business. The passing on and sharing of the mentioned items support the sustainability of the SME, and as a result, bolster the family bond between members as well as the relationship between the enterprise and the community.

Sixaba (2022) highlights that as unemployment rises in townships in South Africa, depending on family heritage has become increasingly vital. This happens because of the family heritage created by SMEs, allowing individuals to build their financial paths, fostering an entrepreneurial atmosphere in communities that can lead to significant socioeconomic advancement. The endurance of family enterprises reflects resilience and flexibility, showcasing how township entrepreneurs can thrive despite systemic challenges (Mokoena, 2022). The influence of family heritage in establishing small enterprises reflects a commitment to honoring the past while innovatively paving the way for future successes and community growth (Maharajh, 2021). This suggests that an individual's sense of self-worth, confidence, and esteem can be shaped by their family background. For example, individuals raised in financially secure, business-oriented families often display higher levels of confidence and self-esteem than those from less privileged backgrounds.

Government Support and Incentives

South Africa and other nations actively encourage entrepreneurship and the growth of small enterprises through a variety of strategies (Rambe & Mosweunyane, 2017). In South Africa, the Small Enterprise Development Agency (SEDA) serves as a key

mechanism for supporting and advancing SMEs (Makgamatha, 2022). According to Mogashoa and Kalitanyi (2023), SEDA in Tshwane Metropolitan Municipality provides a range of services such as business planning, training, and mentorship. This support may contribute to an increase in the number of SMEs in the region, thereby improving their prospects of success. Furthermore, SEDA has established strong partnerships with organizations like the National Empowerment Fund (NEF) and the Sector Education and Training Authority (SETA) to strengthen the development of the SME sector (Saah & Musvoto, 2020). Through these collaborative efforts, SME owners are able to access resources and support that facilitate business growth and sustainability.

The South African government has also implemented fiscal measures to stimulate the SME sector, including a gradual reduction in corporate tax rates, such as the decrease from 29% to 28% in 2009 (Saah & Musvoto, 2020). In addition, the South African Revenue Service (SARS), with support from the presidency, continues to provide tax incentives aimed at promoting SME development. These initiatives create opportunities for SME owners to strengthen their businesses and enhance long-term sustainability. Moreover, the establishment of the National Youth Development Agency (NYDA) under Act 54 of 2008 was intended to address challenges faced by young entrepreneurs (Netshishivhe, 2021). The NYDA offers support to individuals aged 14 to 35 who are starting new businesses or seeking financial assistance for existing ventures. As a result, such initiatives are likely to encourage greater youth participation in entrepreneurship and contribute to the expansion of the SME sector.

Lack of Employment

South Africa features among the nations with the highest unemployment rates globally (Dhoba, Mutema, Akinlade, & Madondo, 2025). The unemployment rate stands at 32.9% for the first quarter of 2023 (Shiferaw, 2025). As stated by Mukwarami and Tengeh (2017) residents engage in SMEs due to a lack of job opportunities and their frustration with remaining idle at home. Pyper (2016) argues that individuals become involved in SMEs due to job losses and feel compelled to launch businesses, rather than from enthusiasm or passion. Consequently, SMEs encounter a significant failure rate since many regard them as a last option and often turn to them when they lack other sources of income (Jayasekara, Fernando, & Ranjani, 2020). Moreover, some engage with SMEs as they aim to create revenue and share it within communities. SMEs are found in every township, facilitating income distribution and providing impoverished residents with the chance to earn income (Fatoki, 2018).

In South Africa's townships, individuals pursue SMEs to gain independence in their work. This guarantees that the residents in the townships have power as they oversee the SMEs (Nkoana, 2025). The decision-making within the SMEs guarantees that individuals in the townships are empowered (Noch & Rumasukun, 2023). Moreover, thriving SMEs in the townships can serve as a model for future SMEs in those areas. This is due to the fact that the successful SME owners will act as role models for individuals in the townships, inspiring them to start their own businesses. Consequently, the small business owner acts as a model for others (Cunha, Kastenholz, & Carneiro, 2020).

Township SMEs are focused on the growth and construction of developments within the townships (Svenson, 2021). For example, SMEs are established in some areas like townships as a tool to help

poor people emerge from a dark place and receive job opportunities (Maloka, 2013). Additionally, residents in the townships can generate income to acquire essential needs in the world (Maloka, 2013). By enabling residents of the townships to acquire essential goods, we can enhance the living standards in these areas (Nkoana, 2025). SMEs are seen as a remedy for social issues (Selelo & Khwela, 2023). SMEs ensure that marginalized individuals, such as unskilled women and youth, are directly involved in the local economy via job opportunities (Maloka, 2013).

Method

Participants

This study sampled 60 SME owners and LED manager via purposive sampling. This target population helps the researchers to reach the aim of the study, which is to investigate the motivational factors of SMEs in Mankweng Township (Zone 1). Furthermore, the majority of the study participants were women (58%), while 42% were men. In terms of age distribution, 30% of the participants were between 18 and 30 years old, and the largest group (45%) fell within the 31 to 40 age range. Additionally, 17% of the participants were aged between 41 and 50, while only 8% were in the 51 to 60 age group.

Research Approach and Study Area

The research employed a mixed methods strategy, focusing on

Mankweng Township (Zone 1) as the study site. Mankweng Township (Zone 1) is located within the Polokwane Local Municipality in Limpopo Province. This location was chosen as the study area due to the rapid growth of SMEs, which act as a strategy to assist the impoverished in obtaining jobs and earning income to purchase essential goods.

Measure

This paper employed a semi-structured questionnaire to gather data from SME owners in Mankweng Township (Zone 1) and a semi-structured interview to collect data from the LED manager in Polokwane Local Municipality.

Data Analysis

This paper used correlational analysis to analyse data from SME owners to analyse quantitative data on the motivation factor of SMEs in Mankweng Township (Zone 1). In addition, this paper used thematic analysis to analyse data from LED manager.

Results

As far as we know, SMEs are established for various reasons in South Africa. Understanding these reasons from a South African context is crucial, the reasons for establishing SMEs in Mankweng Township (Zone 1) are illustrated in Table 1.

Table 1

Motivating Factors of Small and Medium Enterprises in Mankweng Township (Zone 1)

	Market opportunities	Profitability	Passion and vision	Family Legacy	Government support and incentive	Lack of employment	Extra income	Investment
Strongly agree	30%	45%	42%	25%	13%	27%	40%	13%
Agree	40%	43%	47%	50%	58%	53%	45%	55%
Neutral	27%	8%	8	13	20%	20%	12%	24%
Disagree	3%	2%	3%	7%	0%	0%	3%	5%
Strongly disagree	0%	2%	0%	5%	9%	0%	0%	3%
	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Table 1 further illustrates that 70% of the respondents agreed that market opportunities were one of the motivating factors for the SMEs operating in Mankweng Township (Zone 1). As mentioned by Dhlo, this study affirms that it is specific individuals who establish SMEs due to market demand and that they consequently provide the services or products required in the market. The LED manager expressed the notion that it is only with market opportunities that SMEs can function. Hence, it can be inferred that the Mankweng Township (Zone 1) has opportunities that foster entrepreneurial activities, resulting in the establishment and consequently the running of SMEs.

Table 1 shows that 88% of the respondents agree that profitability is an important motivating factor for SMEs in Mankweng Township (Zone 1). This is consistent with the view of Glavee-Geo and Fjortoft (2020), who argue that the pursuit of profit serves as a key motivation for SME owners and employees to participate in economic activities. The LED manager, however, did not agree with the majority view and recommended that SMEs should serve the local community and

not just exploit it for profit. This majority view therefore confirms that profit is an important motivating factor for entrepreneurs and therefore SMEs in the area. This means that profit remains a significant factor that drives the creation of SMEs and their sustainability in the economy.

Table 1 Major themes, descriptions and percentages with reference to existing research findings that correspond with the statements (Table 1) in the Mankweng Township (Zone 1). Table 1 shows that 89% of the respondents that SMEs in Mankweng Township (Zone 1) are motivated by passion and vision in their work. According to Mura and Kajzar (2019), entrepreneurs go into the SME sector because they are passionate about their work and would wish to globalise their businesses. The high agreement with this statement shows that many entrepreneurs may not only be motivated to work hard to ensure that their businesses are profitable but are also very passionate about their businesses. They have a dream of where they would like to see their businesses grow and therefore, hard work to attain their desired dreams is key to the

success of SMEs. Passion and vision for entrepreneurship stimulate the drive towards businesses of interest to the individual. It thus enhances creativity and innovation.

Table 1 shows that 75% of respondents believe that family legacy serves as a motivating factor for SMEs in Mankweng Township (Zone 1). Similarly, KwaZulu-Natal (KZN) notes that research conducted by Maharajh (2021) found that family legacy plays a significant role in shaping SMEs within township economies. The high agreement rate indicates that the establishment of a business is not just seen as a struggle to earn an income, but to carry on the family legacy and tradition, thereby taking care of the family. The LED manager also agreed that people start companies so that their children will not be faced with the challenge of finding employment. The family business can then provide them with jobs.

Table 1 reveals that 70% of respondents agreed that government support and incentives serve as key motivating factors for SMEs in Mankweng Township (Zone 1). In support of this, Rambe and Mosweunyane (2017) argue that government initiatives and incentives encourage individuals to engage in entrepreneurship and contribute to the growth of small businesses in South Africa. The LED manager further highlighted that the Local Economic Development (LED) office provides marketing incubation services to registered SMEs, aiming to offer technical support in the design and implementation of effective marketing strategies that stimulate entrepreneurial activity. Consequently, these government incentives play a significant role in fostering entrepreneurship by creating a conducive economic environment for business development and sustainability.

Table 1 showed that 80% of the participants agreed that the lack of employment is a motivating factor for SMEs in Mankweng Township (Zone 1). The findings by Mukwarami and Tengeh (2017) show that people are motivated to start SMEs in their areas because there is no employment. The LED manager said that "people within Mankweng Township develop start-up businesses to empower themselves within the local economy". SMEs are important to economic growth, the survival of individuals and the stability of communities.

Table 1 reveals that 80% of the respondents agreed that extra income is one of the motivating factors for SMEs in Mankweng Township (Zone 1). The LED manager stated that SMEs could work for people who are employed full time and that it provides an opportunity to earn extra income. These findings corroborate the assertion of Wiid and Cant (2021) that SMEs provide an opportunity for people to earn extra income to fight poverty in South African townships. This, therefore implies that for the people of Mankweng Township (Zone 1) who engage in entrepreneurship, their motivation may be to improve their income levels and to uplift their socioeconomic status. Refer to Table 1: 68% of the respondents agreed that the SMEs are motivated by the investment. Makgamatha (2022) affirms that SMEs are an opportunity in which the community can invest in their townships, thereby creating jobs for them in order to support their families. Thus, investments motivate SMEs.

Discussion

The results presented in Table 1 show that there are various motivational factors that affect the formation and operation within the study area. The majority of the participants (70%) cited market opportunities as an important motivational factor. This shows that

many entrepreneurs in the township are motivated by their willingness to fill existing gaps in the market. This is supported by Dhlomo (2017) who argues that business formation is often motivated by the need to fill existing gaps in the market. The statement by the LED manager also supports this argument, where it is noted that for SMEs to operate effectively, there must be an existing market opportunity. This shows that Mankweng Township (Zone 1) provides an enabling environment for business operation and growth, where entrepreneurs see an opportunity to fill existing gaps while still operating profitably.

Profitability was revealed as the most dominant factor, with 88% of the participants agreeing that the key motivator for the formation of SMEs was for profit. This is in line with Glavee-Geo and Fjrtoft (2020) who proposed that entrepreneurs and workers are mainly driven by the desire for profit in all activities related to enterprises. This, however, does not mean that the entrepreneurs in Mankweng Township are driven by the desire for profit, as the manager warned that the desire for profit was such that it could blind the social obligation of serving the people in the township. However, it was revealed that the entrepreneurs are driven by the desire for sustainability, as 80% of the participants revealed that the key motivator for the formation of SMEs was the desire for additional income.

Other intrinsic aspects, such as passion, vision, and family legacy, were also found to play an important role, with 89% and 75% of the participants identifying these as key motivations, respectively. These findings are in line with the study by Mura and Kajzar (2019) as well as Maharajh (2021) which highlighted that the main reason for entrepreneurship is passion, whether it is for business in general or maintaining the family legacy. The high level of these values indicates that, in addition to the desire for profit, SME owners are emotionally attached to their businesses, with the desire for growth, innovation, and legacy. Moreover, 70% of the participants identified government support/incentives as key, which reiterates the significance of this aspect in promoting entrepreneurialism. The note of the manager of the LED regarding the marketing of incubation services is an additional indicator of the significance of these services in promoting the competitiveness of SMEs. In addition, the lack of employment (80%) and investment opportunities (68%) were key drivers, which reiterates that necessity entrepreneurship is alive and well, with many people entering business not just as an opportunity, but as a means of survival.

Overall, the discussion reveals that the SMEs in Mankweng Township (zone 1) are affected by both opportunity-driven and necessity-driven motivations. Profitability, additional income, and investment opportunities show the entrepreneurs' economic ambitions, while passion, vision, and family legacy show the entrepreneurs' personal ambitions and long-term plans. On the other hand, the lack of employment shows that the entrepreneurs' motivation is also driven by the lack of employment, implying that the entrepreneurs are affected by the lack of employment in the area.

Recommendations

In order to enhance the sustainability and growth of SMEs in South African townships such as Mankweng (Zone 1), it is critical to enhance both intrinsic and extrinsic motivational factors that influence entrepreneurship. The following strategies can be used to address this issue:

- Education on entrepreneurship should be given more emphasis to ensure that small business owners are equipped with appropriate business management skills. This will enable small business owners in townships to change from an opportunity-unfriendly business to an opportunity-friendly business. Collaboration with local municipalities, SEDFA, and local universities, could facilitate this initiative through continued capacity-building workshops.
- The government should also be more strategic in ensuring that motivational challenges facing small business owners in townships are addressed. The incentive schemes should not only focus on financial support but also on building a culture that is creative, innovative, and sustainable. This can be achieved through providing incentives that are linked to specific performance criteria such as innovation output, business expansion, or job creation. On the other hand, LED offices should be strengthened to ensure that small business owners are able to identify new business opportunities as well as expand their customer base.
- Intrinsic motivation should be encouraged through community involvement and family business development. The entrepreneurs should be inspired to pursue business ventures with passion, values, and family visions to sustain business operations. Community development programs should incorporate activities to recognize family businesses, promote knowledge transfer between generations, and provide opportunities to share success stories. The SMEs in Mankweng Township should, therefore, be motivated to pursue passion, visions, and legacies to transcend mere survival to meaningful contributions to economic development.

Conclusion

The purpose of this paper is to investigate the motivational factors of SMEs in Mankweng Township (Zone 1). This paper started with an introduction, problem statements, and the literature. This paper also included the methods and materials used in carrying out the research, findings, and interpretations. Finally, this paper included discussion, recommendations, and conclusions. In a nutshell, the findings of this paper indicate that motivational factors are vital in ensuring the success of SMEs in the area. Motivational factors such as profit or generating additional income are vital in ensuring the success of SMEs. However, overdependence on profit and generating additional income in SMEs may result in neglecting the social responsibility of supporting the local community. Therefore, this paper concludes that it is vital to achieve profit and generate additional income while at the same time ensuring that one fulfills their social responsibility of supporting the local community with dignity and respect. Finally, this paper concludes that in ensuring the sustainability and development of SMEs in South African townships, it is vital to enhance both internal and external motivators that influence entrepreneurial behaviors.

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